

COVID-19 Bibliometrics 28th December 2020 – 3rd January 2021

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A. Medicine and Health

January 1, 2021 (JAMA Int. Med)

Effect of Recombinant Human Granulocyte Colony–Stimulating Factor for Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) and Lymphopenia: A Randomized Clinical Trial

Lin-ling Cheng, Wei-jie Guan, Chong-yang Duan et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.5503>

This randomized clinical trial examines the effect of recombinant human granulocyte colony-stimulating factor on peripheral blood leukocyte and lymphocyte cell counts and clinical improvement in Chinese patients with COVID-19. The authors found that rhG-CSF treatment did not accelerate clinical improvement, however the number of patients progressing to critical illness or death may have been reduced, without an increased risk of serious adverse events suggesting that this treatment should be studied in larger trials.

January 1, 2021 (JAMA Int. Med)

Association Between Early Treatment With Tocilizumab and Mortality Among Critically Ill Patients With COVID-19

Shruti Gupta, Wei Wang, Salim S. Hayek et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.6252>

This multi-centre cohort study assesses mortality rates among patients with COVID-19 admitted to intensive care who were treated with tocilizumab. The risk of in-hospital death was estimated to be lower with tocilizumab treatment in the first 2 days of intensive care unit admission compared with no early use of tocilizumab.

December 31, 2020 (The New England Journal of Medicine)

Safety and Efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 Vaccine

Fernando P. Polack, Stephen J. Thomas, Nicholas Kitchin et al.

<http://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2034577>

BNT162b2 is a lipid nanoparticle–formulated, nucleoside-modified RNA vaccine that encodes a prefusion stabilized, membrane-anchored SARS-CoV-2 full-length spike protein. In this ongoing multinational, placebo-controlled, observer-blinded, pivotal efficacy trial, 21,720 participants received two doses, 21 days apart of the BNT162b2 vaccine candidate (30 µg per dose). BNT162b2 was 95% effective in preventing Covid-19 and similar vaccine efficacy was observed across various subgroups defined by demographics, BMI and presence of co-existing conditions. The safety profile of BNT162b2

was characterized by short-term, mild-to-moderate pain at the injection site, fatigue, and headache. Safety over a median of 2 months was similar to that of other viral vaccines.

December 30, 2020 (The New England Journal of Medicine)

Maintaining Safety with SARS-CoV-2 Vaccines

Mariana C. Castells & Elizabeth J. Philips.

<http://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMra2035343>

In this review article, the authors summarize key findings of various SARS-CoV2 Vaccine trials with a focus on safety and adverse effects. They iterate that careful vaccine-safety surveillance over time, paired with elucidation of mechanisms of adverse events across different SARS-CoV-2 vaccine platforms, will be needed to inform a strategic and systematic approach to vaccine safety.

December 30, 2020 (The New England Journal of Medicine)

Efficacy and Safety of the mRNA-1273 SARS-CoV-2 Vaccine

Lindsey R. Baden, Hana M. El Sahly, Brandon Essink et al.

<http://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2035389>

The mRNA-1273 vaccine is a lipid nanoparticle–encapsulated mRNA-based vaccine that encodes the prefusion stabilized full-length spike protein of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. 15,210 participants received 2 doses of the mRNA-1273 vaccine in phase 3 randomized, observer-blinded, placebo-controlled trial which was conducted at 99 centres across the United States. The mRNA-1273 vaccine showed 94.1% efficacy at preventing Covid-19 illness, including severe disease. Aside from transient local and systemic reactions, no safety concerns were identified.

December 18, 2020 (Nat Rev Immunol)

Viral targets for vaccines against COVID-19

Dai, L, Gao, G.F.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41577-020-00480-0>

Several vaccine candidates have been developed, several of which have completed late-stage clinical trials and are reporting positive results. In this Progress article, the authors discuss which viral elements are used in COVID-19 vaccine candidates, why they might act as good targets for the immune system and the implications for protective immunity.

B. Science and Engineering

December 10, 2020 (Scientific Reports)

Tracking the early depleting transmission dynamics of COVID-19 with a time-varying SIR model

Kian Boon Law, Kalaiarasu M. Peariasamy, Balvinder Singh Gill et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-78739-8>

The authors modified the SIR model to simulate the early depleting transmission dynamics of COVID-19 to better predict its trend in Malaysia. The classical SIR model was fitted to observed total, active and removed cases before lockdown to estimate the basic reproduction number. They then modified the model with a partial time-varying force of infection. The modified SIR model was used to analyse observed data over 6 weeks during the lockdown. They concluded that the depleting transmission dynamics during lockdown can be accurately captured by the time-varying SIR model.

December 10, 2020 (Scientific Reports)

Multidisciplinary approach to COVID-19 risk communication: a framework and tool for individual and regional risk assessment

Rishi Ram Parajuli, Bhogendra Mishra, Amrit Banstola et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-78779-0>

This paper presents a framework to assess the individual and regional risk of COVID-19 along with risk communication tools. Relative risk scores on a scale of 100 represent the integrated risk factors. The personal risk model includes age, exposure history, symptoms, local risk and existing health condition, whereas regional risk is calculated through the actual cases of COVID-19, public health risk factors, socioeconomic condition and immigration statistics. A web application tool (<http://www.covira.info>) was developed for one to assess the risk and find the information links primarily for Nepal. This study provides regional risk for Nepal, but the framework is scalable for other countries.

November 11, 2020 (Scientific Reports)

COVID-Net: a tailored deep convolutional neural network design for detection of COVID-19 cases from chest X-ray images

Linda Wang, Zhong Qiu Lin, Alexander Wong

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-76550-z>

COVID-Net, a deep convolutional neural network is for the detection of COVID-19 cases from chest X-ray images that are open source and available to the general public. They introduce COVIDx, an open-access benchmark dataset comprising of 13,975 images with the largest number of publicly available COVID-19 positive cases. Furthermore, they investigate how COVID-Net makes predictions using an explainability method to discover deeper insights,

C. Social Sciences, Humanities and Public Policies

January 9, 2021 (Journal of Urban Economics)

The geographic spread of COVID-19 correlates with the structure of social networks as measured by Facebook

Theresa Kuchler, Dominic Russel & Johannes Stroebel.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jue.2020.103314>

This US study used aggregated data from Facebook to show that COVID-19 is more likely to spread between regions with stronger social network connections. Areas with more social ties to two early COVID-19 “hotspots” (Westchester County, NY, in the U.S. and Lodi province in Italy) generally had more confirmed COVID-19 cases by the end of March. These relationships hold after controlling for geographic distance to the hotspots as well as the population density and demographics of the regions.

As the pandemic progressed in the U.S., a county’s social proximity to recent COVID-19 cases and deaths predicts future outbreaks over and above physical proximity and demographics. In part due to its broad coverage, social connectedness data provides additional predictive power to measures based on smartphone location or online search data.

The authors suggest that these findings indicate that data from online social networks can be useful to epidemiologists and others hoping to forecast the spread of communicable diseases such as COVID-19.

January 6, 2021 (Humanities and Social Sciences Communications)

Responding to the pandemic as a family unit: social impacts of COVID-19 on rural migrants in China and their coping strategies

Shuangshuang Tang & Xin Li

<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-020-00686-6>

There has been limited research on the social impacts of epidemics on uninfected people in developing countries. This study investigates the social impacts of the spread of COVID-19 on rural migrants and their coping strategies through face-to-face interviews with rural migrants in Nanjing, China. The study finds that rural migrants suffered from serious social impacts due to COVID-19, especially during the associated lockdown period. Since they received little support from governments and employers, rural migrants adopted household strategies to deal with difficulties. They helped one another within a household as a unit to maximize resources and reduce risks. Traditional family values were helpful during the period.

December 26, 2020 (Safety Science)

Government policies, national culture and social distancing during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic: International evidence

Yan Wang

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2020.105138>

The authors assess the impact of national culture and government policies on social distancing to fight COVID-19 across major economies during the first wave of the pandemic. They do this by regressing government stringency index from the Oxford COVID-19 government response tracker together with Hofstede's national culture scores on social distancing data from Google mobility reports.

Government stringency is found to have a far larger impact on social distancing than national culture. Social distancing increases with government stringency and decreases with the cultural factor 'Long-term Orientation'; the opposite is true for the cultural 'Indulgence'. Results indicate that policymakers must act decisively rather than allowing for cultural factors.

December 25, 2020 (Health Policy and Technology)

Effects of the COVID-19 pandemic in India: An analysis of policy and technological interventions

Isha Goel, Seema Sharma & Smita Kashiramka.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlpt.2020.12.001>

This study uses secondary data to analyse the underlying epidemiological situation in India and explain the possible impacts of policy and technological changes. The spread of COVID-19 in India was initially characterized by lower case numbers and fewer deaths compared with numbers in many developed countries. This was mainly due to stringent lockdown and demographic factors. However, economic constraints forced a staggering lockdown exit strategy, resulting in a spike in COVID-19 cases in June 2020. Subsequently, India became the third-worst affected country worldwide. Low spending on health as a percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) meant there was a shortage of hospital beds and ventilators and a lack of medical personnel, especially in the public health sector. Nevertheless, technological advances, supported by a strong research base, helped contain the health and economic damage resulting from the pandemic.

The authors posit that measures such as asymptomatic testing, public-private partnerships, and technological advances will be essential until a vaccine against COVID-19 can be developed and rolled-out in India.

December 22, 2020 (Public Health in Practice)

Early detection of change patterns in COVID-19 incidence and the implementation of public health policies: a multi-national study

Steven S. Coughlin, Ayten Yigiter, Honyan Xu et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhip.2020.100064>

For this multi-national study, the authors examined data from 20 countries in Europe, the Americas, Africa, Eastern Mediterranean and West Pacific regions, and aggregated daily new case data for the European Union including 27 countries were used. The analysis enabled the identification of possible change or turning points as indicated by the dynamics of daily COVID-19 incidences. Days when change points were detected, were ahead of the actual policy implementation days. In most countries included in this study, the decision lagged the change point days by too long a period to prevent potential widespread extension of the pandemic. The authors suggest that globally, social distancing measures may have been most effective in smaller countries with single governmental and public health organizations.